

OBESITY, METABOLIC SYNDROME AND CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE

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Background: The metabolic syndrome is a disorder that includes dyslipidemia, insulin resistance, and hypertension and is associated with an increased risk of diabetes and cardiovascular disease. We determined whether patterns of regional fat deposition are associated with metabolic syndrome in older adults.

Methods: The study design was a comparative study of two retrospective analytical studies. The main source of information in the study was primary patient data, namely medical outpatient records. The study was approved and permitted by the “REPUBLICAN SPECIALIZED CARDIOLOGICAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL MEDICAL CENTER KHOREZM BRANCH” (protocol No. 09/2184 07/04/2022). Metabolic syndrome was defined by Adult Treatment Panel III criteria, including serum triglyceride level, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol level, glucose level, blood pressure, and waist circumference.

Key words: ASCVD-atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease; BMI-body mass index; CHD-coronary heart disease; CRPC-reactive protein; CVD-cardiovascular disease; HDL-highdensity lipoprotein; IGT-impaired glucose tolerance; LDL-low-density lipoprotein; NEFA-nonesterified fatty acid; PAI-plasminogen activator inhibitor; TGRLP-triglyceride-rich lipoprotein; VLDL-very LDL; BMI-Body mass index.

Criteria for metabolic syndrome

On the basis of recently defined criteria, persons were characterized as having the metabolic syndrome if they had at least 3 of the following conditions: 1) waist circumference greater than 102 cm in men and 88 cm in women; 2) serum triglyceride level of 150 mg/dL (1.7 mmol/L) or greater; 3) high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol level less than 40 mg/dL (1.0 mmol/L) in men and 50 mg/dL (1.3 mmol/L) in women; 4) blood pressure of 130/85 mm Hg or greater; and 5) serum glucose level of 110 mg/dL (6.1 mmol/L) or more. In addition, individuals who reported currently using antihypertensive or antidiabetic medication were counted as meeting the high blood pressure or glucose criterion, respectively. Age of participants was determined to the nearest year. Standing height and weight were measured in stocking feet and with light clothing, and body mass index (BMI) was calculated as weight in kilograms

divided by the square of height in meters, to characterize men and women who were of normal weight (BMI, <25.0), overweight (BMI, 25.0-29.9), and obese (BMI, >29.9). Total body fat was determined by means of dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry (QDR 4500; Hologic Inc, Waltham, Mass). Waist circumference was determined to the nearest centimeter. Blood was drawn after an overnight fast and analyzed for serum triglycerides, HDL cholesterol, and glucose determinations. Serum triglycerides and HDL cholesterol were measured on a chemistry analyzer (Vitros 950; Johnson & Johnson, Raritan, NJ). Plasma glucose was measured by means of an automated glucose oxidase reaction (YSI 2300 Glucose Analyzer; Yellow Springs Instruments, Yellow Springs, Ohio). A conventional mercury sphygmomanometer was used for the measurement of blood pressure. The participant rested quietly in a seated position with the back supported and feet flat on the ground for at least 5 minutes before the blood pressure measurement. Systolic and diastolic blood pressures were defined as the average of 2 measures.

Categories of obesity

Obesity is rampant in the Central Asia and is becoming increasingly common worldwide. The increase in obesity prevalence is due to two major factors, plentiful supplies of inexpensive foods and sedentary jobs. Both are driven in no small part by technology. Thanks to technology, production of large quantities of cheap food is possible, and manual work is rapidly disappearing. In areas of the world in which these advances have not penetrated, obesity is not a significant public health problem. Thus, obesity is a direct result of technological advance and represents a major challenge for technological society. Obesity must also be recognized as a product of free society in which a multitude of food choices and job opportunities are available. A public health approach to the problem of obesity that restricts choice will not be acceptable to a free society. This fact puts increased responsibility on the individual to recognize the underlying causes of obesity and modify behavior to reduce the personal burden of obesity.

That obesity extracts a social cost is well recognized. The costs in physical health are less well recognized by the general public. The foremost physical consequence of obesity is atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD)[1]. A substantial portion of the ASCVD resulting from obesity is mediated by type 2 diabetes. But obesity is accompanied by several other risk factors for ASCVD. The sum of the risk factors that predisposes to ASCVD goes by the name of metabolic syndrome. In addition, obesity is accompanied by other medical complications other than ASCVD and diabetes; these include fatty liver, cholesterol gallstones, sleep apnea, osteoarthritis, and polycystic ovary disease. These disorders are commonly found in individuals who carry the metabolic syndrome.

Obesity can be defined as an excess of body fat. A surrogate marker for body fat content is the body mass index (BMI), which is determined by weight (kilograms) divided by height squared (square meters). In clinical terms, a BMI of 25–29 kg/m² is called overweight; higher BMIs (30 kg/m²) are called obesity (4). A better way to define obesity would be in terms of percent total body fat (4). This can be measured by several methods (skin-fold thickness, bioelectrical impedance, underwater weighing). In terms of percent body fat, obesity can be defined as 25% or greater in men and 35% or greater in women. The measurement of percent body fat is rarely used in clinical practice, however, because of inconvenience and cost. The best way to estimate obesity in clinical practice is to measure waist circumference. This is because an excess of abdominal fat is most tightly associated with the metabolic risk factors. In the United States, abdominal obesity is defined as a waist circumference in men of 102 cm or more and in women of 88 cm or more[2]. In other countries, lesser increases in waist circumferences have been associated with metabolic risk factors, and other standards are in use.

Atherogenic dyslipidemia: This condition is characterized by an increase in elevated triglycerides (and increased VLDL particle number), increased small LDL particles, and low HDL cholesterol [3]. It is commonly present in obese persons. The increased number of VLDL and LDL particles accounts for the increased level of total apo B usually observed with atherogenic dyslipidemia. The atherogenic potential of each lipoprotein abnormality has long been a topic of great interest but one that is not fully resolved. For many years triglyceride-rich lipoproteins (TGRLPs) were thought not to be atherogenic. Nonetheless, there is growing evidence that smaller TGRLP (remnant lipoproteins) are in fact atherogenic [4]. This evidence comes from studies in laboratory animals, patients with genetic disorders causing remnant accumulation, metaanalysis of epidemiological studies, and clinical trials [1]. TGRLPs as a class are a mixture of lipoproteins, and it has been difficult to differentiate between atherogenic and nonatherogenic forms of TGRLPs. Nonetheless, there is a growing consensus among investigators that TGRLP fraction definitely contains atherogenic lipoproteins.

Statistical analysis

Prevalence of metabolic syndrome, demographics, body composition, and regional AT variables were described, and the differences in continuous variables between those with and without metabolic syndrome were evaluated by either *t* tests or the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. Categorical differences between persons with and without the metabolic syndrome were evaluated with the χ^2 test. To assess sex-specific associations between regional AT distribution and metabolic syndrome, multiple logistic regression by maximum likelihood method was used to model the probability of metabolic syndrome as a function of each component of regional fat distribution separately after adjusting for race, smoking, and physical activity along with pertinent

2-factor interaction terms within each BMI stratum after stratifying by sex. Point estimates and the associated confidence interval for all the independent variables were obtained, multicollinearity was tested by variance inflation factor, and the model evaluation was done by Hosmer-Lemeshow statistic. Since the results were similar for BMI and total body fat strata, we present findings for only BMI strata. Current smoking status and physical activity were assessed by questionnaire. All analyses were performed with Microsoft office Excel 2020.

Results

Prevalence and characteristics of metabolic syndrome

The study analyzed 80 reviewers who were hospitalized or treated as outpatients over a period of time from 2021 to 2023. Of the reviewers, 40/50% are men, and 40/50% are women. Of these, 70/87.5% were patients with hypertension, 50/62.5% were patients with coronary artery disease, and 30/37.5% patients with type 2 diabetes diagnosed in accordance with the provisions, reflected in national cardiology guidelines. Clinical characteristics of this group of patients are presented in Table 1.

Feature	n	%
Hypertension or established diagnosis of hypertension	59/70	73.75%/87.5%
Abdominal obesity	59	73.75%
Dyslipidemia		
- Hypertriacylglycerolemia	36	45%
- Increased LDL concentrations		
- Decreased HDL concentrations	56	70%
	22	27.5%

Summary

Obesity is a major underlying risk factor for ASCVD. It is associated with multiple ASCVD risk factors, and it also is a risk factor for type 2 diabetes. Diabetes itself is a cardiovascular risk factor. Despite the strong association between obesity and ASCVD, the mechanisms underlying this relationship are not well understood. Our understanding of the connection between obesity and vascular disease is complicated by a plethora of possibilities. Obesity acts on so many metabolic pathways, producing so many potential risk factors, that it is virtually impossible to differentiate between the more important and less important. The possibilities for confounding variables are enormous. This complexity provides a great challenge for basic and clinical research. It also raises the possibility for new targets of therapy for the metabolic syndrome. With this said, the fundamental challenge is how to intervene at the public health level

to reduce the high prevalence of obesity in the general population. This approach offers the greatest possibility for reducing the cardiovascular risk that accompanies obesity.

References

1. Grundy SM, Hansen B, Smith Jr SC, Cleeman JI, Kahn RA; American Heart Association; National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute; American Diabetes Association 2004 Clinical management of metabolic syndrome: report of the American Heart Association/National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute/ American Diabetes Association conference on scientific issues related to management. *Circulation* 109:551–556.
2. 1998 Clinical Guidelines on the Identification, Evaluation, and Treatment of Overweight and Obesity in Adults—the Evidence Report. National Institutes of Health. *Obes Res* 6(Suppl 2):51S–209S.
3. National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III) 2002 Third Report of the National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III) final report. *Circulation* 106:3143–3421.
4. Krauss RM 1998 Atherogenicity of triglyceride-rich lipoproteins. *Am J Cardiol* 81:13B–17B.